

ANALYSIS OF A SIMPLE AND MULTILAYER FSS WITH A BIO-INSPIRED ELEMENT FOR WLAN APPLICATIONS

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Abstract - This article aims to present a single and multilayer Frequency Selective Surface (FSS) with bio-inspired element geometry, with filtering capability (blocking/rejection) to the 2.4 GHz WLAN frequency band.

Keywords: FSS; Bio-inspired element; WLAN; FSS multiband; Polarization independence.

INTRODUCTION

Frequency Selective Surfaces (FSSs) are widely known for their ability to filter electromagnetic waves that operate within specific frequency ranges in free space, either by blocking or transmitting them, which is why they are also referred to as spatial filters. They are planar and periodic structures composed of elements such as apertures or conductive patches and are used in various applications, including wireless communications [1].

Therefore, in this article, an FSS is proposed to filter the frequency spectrum of WLAN applications that operate in the 2.4 GHz band, ranging from 2400 to 24800 MHz, following the 802.11b/g/n standards [2].

DEVELOPMENT

The computationally proposed and developed FSS consists of the triple repetition of the bio-inspired element in the shape of an eight-petal flower. Fig. 1 shows the geometry of the unit cell of the element.

Figure 1 – Unit cell with the geometry of the element.

The use of this geometry was motivated by [3], a work in which the authors employed the Gielis formula to generate elements whose geometry aims to replicate shapes found in nature.

The Gielis formula is described in Eq. 1, with one of its arguments being $m/4$ of the angle θ , which

directly influences the generation of the chosen symmetry pattern. Note that, in Eq. 1, the variables n_i , $m \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (positive real numbers) and $a, b \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (non-zero positive real numbers) [4].

$$r(\theta) = \left[\left| \frac{1}{a} \cos\left(\frac{m}{4}\theta\right)^{n_2} \right| + \left| \frac{1}{b} \sin\left(\frac{m}{4}\theta\right)^{n_3} \right| \right]^{\frac{1}{n_1}} \quad (1)$$

In this work, it was conventionally designated the outermost flower in Figure 1 as the first flower, the middle one as the second flower, and the innermost one as the third flower. Thus, the first flower has a height of 74.412mm and a width of 13.8701 mm between the petals. The second flower has a height of 52.0884 mm, while the width between the petals is 9.2467 mm. The third flower, on the other hand, has a height of 29.7648 mm and a width of 4.6234 mm between the petals. The spacing between each of the flowers is 7.4412 mm, and the inner width of the flowers is 3.7206 mm.

The structure's periodicity is 80.613 mm, and the dielectric substrate used was FR4 Epoxy, with a relative permittivity of 4.4, a dielectric loss tangent of 0.02, and a material thickness of 3.2 mm. Furthermore, the cascading of the structure was done with 10 mm, 15 mm, 20 mm, 25 mm, and 30 mm of air, as shown in Fig. 2, which is cascaded with 20 mm of air. It's worth noting that using multilayer or cascaded FSSs tends to increase the bandwidth of the frequency response in terms of the transmission coefficient [5].

Figure 2 – Cascaded FSS element with 20mm of air.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulations of the single-layer and multi-layer FSSs used the Method of Moments, and their results are displayed in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. One of the characteristics observed in both results is the polarization independence of the structure, meaning that regardless of the field in which the wave is incident (electric or magnetic), its behavior will be quite similar.

In the single-layer structure, you can observe a filtering band that ranges from 2.409 GHz to 2.599 GHz, resulting in a bandwidth of 190 MHz, with a resonance frequency at 2.51 GHz. The current distribution at 2.51 GHz can be seen in Fig. 5. Also, note in Fig. 3 that this structure filters most of the 2.4GHz WLAN operating band.

Figure 3 – Simulated results obtained in terms of the transmission coefficient for the single-layer FSS.

Figure 4 – Simulated results obtained in terms of the transmission coefficient for the multilayer FSS.

Figure 5 – Simulated current distribution at 2.51 GHz in the single-layer FSS.

When analyzing Fig. 4, it's noticeable in the multilayer FSS that, as expected, as the air layer thickness increases, there is an increase in the rejection bandwidth of the structure for WLAN applications operating at 2.4 GHz, effectively filtering out this application band, ranging from 2400 to 24800 MHz.

In the case of cascading with 30 mm of air, the bandwidth starts at 2.265 GHz and ends at 2.645 GHz, that is, it doubled, going from 190 MHz to 380 MHz, when compared to the simple structure. Additionally, the resonance frequency of the cited multilayer FSS occurs at 2.485 GHz.

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